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Template to a self-administered questionnaire on public's risk perception of man-made chemicals in the human body; perception, acceptability, knowledge, beliefs, perceived control, information use, needs and understanding

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1 Authors and acknowledgements

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This template to a risk perception questionnaire on man-made chemicals in the human body draws heavily on earlier. We gratefully acknowledge the contributions from variety of (international) projects on risk perception at RIVM, which were (in part) performed in the framework of the strategic research programme (<https://www.rivm.nl/en/about-rivm/knowledge-and-expertise/strategic-programme-rivm>). These include the project 'Non-specific physical symptoms in relation to the actual and perceived exposure to EMF and the underlying mechanisms; a multidisciplinary approach' (Baliatsas, 2015, 'Emphasis'), the more recent project 'Perceptions of Uncertain Risks in Societal Groups' (PurSa(n)g) (Jansen et al, 2018, Jansen et al, 2020, Jansen, 2020 in press) and the project 'Toolkit of instruments measuring and understanding risk perceptions' (TINBER, 2019).

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2 Glossary

E-PVQ	Environmental Portrait Values Questionnaire
HBM	Human biomonitoring
LOT	Life Orientation Test
MHW	Modern Health Worries
PASA	Primary Appraisal Secondary Appraisal questionnaire
PC	Perceived control
REI-10	Rational-Experiential Inventory
SES	Socio-economic status

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3 Abstract/Summary

This report presents the template to a self-administered questionnaire on public's risk perception of man-made chemicals in the human body. It is theory-based and founded on earlier work on risk perception, mainly within the Strategic Programme RIVM. From the literature, we observe that topics such as personal traits, beliefs about health impacts, trust in authorities, attitudes toward the chemicals themselves and toward dealing with uncertainty, are all relevant topics in the context of risk perceptions, information needs and need for further policy development. The template includes sections on risk perception, acceptability, knowledge, beliefs, perceived control, information use, needs and understanding.

The report outlines the background to the topic, the (lack of) literature specific to the study of perception targeted to man-made chemical in the human body, as measured through HBM. The report and questionnaire material is structured in four sections: A Demographics and perceived health; B Perception of risk of chemicals and chemical substances in body; C Explanatory factors for risk perception (general and personal); and D Information use, needs and understanding. The report provides origin, background and references to the questions and outlines possible approaches to the statistical analysis of collected materials. Proposed questions are listed in the annexes.

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4 Introduction and background

In the initial Description of Activities of HBM4EU, under WP7, Task 7.3: Questionnaires development, it was foreseen that questions on risk perceptions of HBM would be included in the general questionnaire. Given the extensive length of the questionnaire and the absence of clear hypotheses about risk perception in relation to actual HBM values, it was decided not to include risk perception questions in the general questionnaire under Task 7.3. Nonetheless, the need was felt to have standard risk perception questions relevant in the HBM context available under WP7 for possible use by the partners in HBM4EU and in other (EU) projects, e.g. in exposome studies. This report provides a brief overview of backgrounds on risk perceptions, lay peoples mental models (values, beliefs, knowledge), elements of risk perception which might provide starting points for communication and policy debate and action. It also contains a core set of questions on these elements.

The general research question in the context of risk perception of Human Biomonitoring (HBM) in the general public is: How do people perceive the presence of man-made chemical substances in the human body as assessed by HBM, in terms of risks, perceived control, information use and needs, and overall acceptability and how do these aspects relate to underlying values, beliefs and knowledge (mental models)?

More specific questions are:

- What do people know and think of HBM and to what extent do they feel control over presence of man-made chemical substances in their body?
- How do personal characteristics (be it traits or states) like self-efficacy, trust, environmental health literacy and environmental values/ attitudes relate to risk perceptions in the general public?
- How do risk perceptions relate to behavioural intentions, information needs and need for policy interventions?

This questionnaire contains four sets of questions:

Part A: Demographics and perceived health

Part B: Perception of risk of chemicals and chemical substances in the human body

Part C: Explanatory factors for risk perception (general and personal)

Part D: Information (needs, use, and key channels and understanding of information

Where possible questions were derived from existing questionnaires and paraphrased toward man-made chemicals in the human body. To the degree possible, we maintained the original scales from existing questionnaires. As a consequence, questions have different answer scales, the advantage being optimal external comparability of results. Questions addressing perception of chemicals in the environment and questions from the Eurobarometer were adopted to allow internal and external comparison and reference. The questionnaire contains a set of modules. Depending on the research question, modules can be chosen from it. It is not advisable to make a selection at item level. (see also under section 4).

This operationalisation of risk perception draws from the body of literature on the topic as compiled and further developed in a variety of (international) projects on risk perception at RIVM, which were performed in the framework of the strategic research programme (<https://www.rivm.nl/en/about-rivm/knowledge-and-expertise/strategic-programme-rivm>). The literature is described in more detail in the following references. These include the project 'Non-specific physical symptoms in relation to the actual and perceived exposure to EMF

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and the underlying mechanisms; a multidisciplinary approach' (Baliatsas, 2015, 'Emphasis'), the more recent project 'Perceptions of Uncertain Risks in Societal Groups' (PurSa(n)g) (Jansen et al, 2018, Jansen et al, 2020, Jansen, 2020 in press) and the project 'Toolkit of instruments measuring and understanding risk perceptions' (TINBER, 2019).

5 Risk perception: a short summary

The general public, concerned citizens, NGO's, professional groups and policy makers evaluate risks along different dimensions and tend to emphasize different aspects of the same risk. Perceptions of risk and coping with them differ per hazard as well as per societal group (Briggs 2011) and are only partly dependent on the type of risk. People think differently about the acceptability of risks depending on the values and views they hold. Some risks, especially when there is an external cause, may easily create public commotion (Petrie 2001). This would also apply to the case of man-made chemicals (Miles 2003, Eurobarometer_Special_314 2009).

From a risk-communication point of view it is important to study differences in perception in the general public of incomparable risks that are judged as voluntary versus un-voluntary, known or unknown, natural versus artificial, threatening versus not threatening etc. Perceptions of risks, perceived control over a risk and strategies to cope with risks and accompanying levels of acceptance vary across different risk problems. These perceptions are dependent on the characteristic of hazards themselves, but also on the social group one belongs to. Whether a risk is considered as acceptable is strongly culturally determined and dependent on the values of that group. Based on previous studies, we know what factors these different groups focus on when evaluating and interpreting the results of a risk assessment. Risk can be compared based on these factors and characteristics and this offers anchor-points for decisions on information needs in the general population. A good balance between these needs and the expert information is important for successful risk communication.

On top of the recent evaluation of the literature on risk perception within the context of the Pur Sang and TINBER projects an additional literature scan on risk perception targeted to human biomonitoring was performed in Scopus, using ("Risk perception" AND "human biomonitoring") as search terms, revealed only seven publications in October 2018. An update in July 2020 identified 19 publications. Most of these publications, however, were not focused on studying the risk perception in relation to HBM, and did not use the term but it showed up in the engineered keywords in Scopus and used the term HBM in a different context. Only three publications were specifically targeted at risk perceptions in the context of HBM studies. Neither of those directly addressed how people perceive *man-made chemicals in their body*. The first one concerned the Flemish Biomonitoring Programme and risk communication (Keune, Morrens and Loot 2008) and shares results and insights from a Belgian HBM study. The second one, Coi et al. (2016) explored risk perception in four areas with arsenic pollution in Italy. The third by Bena et al. (2019) assessed risk perception of people living near solid waste incinerator plants near Turin, prior to a health surveillance programme that would include HBM. Overall, the most pertinent publications focused more on perceptions about (local) environmental pollution and on trust and information needs in the context of an ongoing, or planned future HBM study. To our knowledge, no study has directly assessed our primary research question, i.e. "How do people perceive the presence of man-made chemical substances in the human body as assessed by HBM".

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Possibly, some other targeted publications are available in the grey literature. To our knowledge, no multi-centre studies on cross-cultural differences exist on this topic. Nonetheless, such differences are likely to exist, based on cross-cultural differences in risk perception in general (Renn 2000) and more specifically in Europe as was shown by e.g. EuroBarometer studies (Jowel et al, 2007) and differences observed in 'environment concern' between European countries (Istamto, Houthuijs et al. 2014) (Brown et al, 2011).

In the Flemish Biomonitoring Programme, several questions on risk perception were presented to participants. These covered a range of topics and included questions about the perceived prevalence of environmental problems, the impact of these on the participant's health and their families, the levels of trust in authorities, participation in the debate, and willingness to participate in a risk perception study. (Keune, Morrens and Loots 2008). No questions were included on the perception of risk regarding the presence of man-made chemical substances in the human body.

The expected cross-cultural differences in Europe, combined with the absence of (multi-centre/multi-country) studies on the risk perception of the presence of man-made chemical substances in the human body as assessed by HBM, warrants further study in HBM4EU and in subsequent activities and other projects under Horizon Europe. To facilitate such studies, this report provides a set of questions pertinent to risk perception of chemical substances in the body and to determinants of risk perception.

6 The structure of the questionnaire

The template to a questionnaire on public's risk perception of man-made chemicals in the human body is set up as a self-administered questionnaire. We anticipate the use via online administration, possibly in existing panels. Online administration would involve adaptation of the layout of questions, suitable for web-based utilisation. This may include changes to the numbering of questions and items.

The questionnaire is theory-based and grounded in the general literature on risk perception. In the absence of literature on risk perception studies targeted to HBM, we adapted existing question frames to HBM. The template comprises four parts. The first covers standard demographic information and questions on perceived health. The second comprise questions on perception of chemicals in the direct environment and in the human body. The third part consists of questions addressing potential explanatory variables of perception. The fourth and final part covers use and understanding of risk information. The origin and background of the proposed questions are described in Section 7. The numbering of questions in A1 corresponds to initial numbering in HBM4EU Basic questionnaire from 2018¹. Subsequent questions only carry item numbers (*ix*), starting with *112* in section A2.

6.1 PART A: Demographics and perceived health

A1: Personal Information [derived from HBM4EU's main questionnaire, numbering corresponds to main questionnaire numbering] [Q1-11](#)

A2: Self-reported health [112-17](#)

¹ Note that later 'single substance questionnaires' use a different breakdown and numbering of questions and sections (c.f. <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/?mdocs-cat=mdocs-cat-21&mdocs-att=null>)

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6.2 PART B: Perception of risk of chemicals and chemical substances in body

B1: Risk perception of chemical substances in the environment [118-34](#)

B2: Appraisal (primary and secondary) of chemicals in the body [135-50](#)

B3: Risk perception of chemicals in body [151-67](#)

6.3 PART C: Explanatory factors for risk perception (general and personal)

C1: Modern health worries [168-99](#)

C2: Trust in regulation of chemical substances by (national). [1100-111111](#)

C3: Environmental Portrait Values Questionnaire (E-PVQ [1112-128](#)

C4-5 Beliefs, knowledge and feelings about chemical substances; in general (C4) [1129-136](#) and in the body (C5) [1137-150](#),

C6: Environmental sensitivity. [1151-158](#)

C7 Health literacy [1159-170](#)

C8: Self efficacy [1171-178](#)

6.4 PART D: Information use, needs and understanding

D1: Sources of information [1179-193](#)

D2: Need for cognition [1194-205](#)

D3. Understanding HBM risk information (An example text). [1206-215](#)

7 Origin and background of the questions

Most questions included are based on standard and validated indices. In case of standard questions and in view of comparability the wording as well as the direction of the scales were not altered. As a consequence, the direction in scaling (from positive to negative or reversed) differs between questions. Reversed questions are often included in multi-item instruments to avoid that people score “automatically” and to safeguard attention. Below, the origin of the questions or adapted questions are presented following the structure of the questionnaire.

7.1 Section A: Demographics and perceived health

7.1.1 A1: Demographics

The questionnaire includes questions on socio-demographic characteristics such as age, gender, ethnicity, education, occupational status, type of residence and home ownership status. These questions (1-4, 6, 7-9, 11) are derived from the initial HBM4EU Basic questionnaire from 2018. Note that later ‘single substance questionnaires’ use a different

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breakdown and numbering of questions and sections (c.f. <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/?mdocs-cat=mdocs-cat-21&mdocs-att=null>).

7.1.2 A2: General health

General health is measured by the perceived health index of the Rand36. This index contains five questions related to general health and one added question about perceived health change. The general health questions of the RAND36 measure the subjective evaluation of the general health status. A low score on the scale indicates that a person evaluates his/her health as bad or expects that his/her health will deteriorate. In the last question people are asked to evaluate their current health with that of a year ago. Responses are provided on a 6 point Likert ranging from definitely true (0) to definitely false (5). The RAND36 questions can be applied modular and have a long history of proven reliability and validity. (Ware and Sherbourg, 1992)

7.2 Section B Perception of risk of chemicals and chemical substances in body.

The questions in this section are based on a questionnaire developed in PurSa(n)g project (Janssen et al, 2018, 2020) (Jansen, 2020) and enriched with questions from psychometric paradigm of Slovic (Fischhof et al, Slovic, 1980, 1981, 1987) and Keune, Morrens and Loots (2008, 2012), The Portrait Value Questionnaire for environmental issues by Bouman, Steg and Keirs (2018); and Primary and Secondary Appraisal Questionnaire by Gaab et al, (2009).

7.2.1 B1: Risk perception of chemical in the environment

A semantic differential based on Jansen 2020 concerning attitude towards chemicals in the environment and the key psychometric dimensions of Slovic et al. such as threat, fear, unknown, voluntary, controllable, fatal etc. (Fischhof et al, 1980); Slovic, et al, 1980, 1981, 1987) on a 5-point scale people can indicate their perception of risk related to chemical substances. These questions can be used for external reference and for internal comparison with the questions of B3 on risk perception of chemicals in the body.

7.2.2 B2: Primary and secondary appraisal of chemicals in the environment

Key concepts in the stress and coping models of Lazarus and Folkman (1984) are primary and secondary appraisal. Primary appraisal refers to the evaluation of a threat and secondary appraisal to the level of control one perceives. The PASA (Primary Appraisal Secondary Appraisal questionnaire by Gaab, 2009) measures these dimensions and consists of four situation-specific subscales assessing challenge (four items; example item: "The situation is important for me"; Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.36^2$) and threat (four items; example item: "I do not feel threatened by the situation"; $\alpha = 0.82$), which form the primary appraisal subscale ($\alpha = 0.61$), in addition to self-concept of own competencies (four items; example item: "I know what I have to do in this situation"; $\alpha = 0.88$) and control expectancy (four

² Cronbach's alpha is a measure of internal consistency, that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group. It is considered to be a measure of scale reliability.

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items; example item: "I can control a lot myself of what I can do in this situation"; $\alpha = 0.57$), which form the secondary appraisal subscale ($\alpha = 0.66$). From these questions a so called stress index can be derived by subtracting the secondary appraisal from the primary appraisal mean scores (see Gaab, 2009).

7.2.3 B3: Risk perception of chemicals in the body

Similar as in B1, a semantic differential was made based on Jansen 2020 concerning attitude towards chemicals in human body and key elements of Slovic' psychometric dimensions (1987) of fear, unknown, voluntary, controllable, fatal etc. on a 5-point scale people can indicate their perception of risk related to chemical substances.

7.3 Section C: Explanatory factors for risk perception (general and personal)

Section C consists of sets of questions known from the literature to cover covariates that are associated with and may affect risk perception. This will allow researchers to study associations of covariates with risk perception of chemicals in the body observed in their study population. Moreover, insight into e.g. 'health literacy' of study participants and its relation to risk perception of chemicals in the body may assist researchers in communication of information on HBM levels and associated risks to their target audience/study population.

7.3.1 C1: Modern Health Worries

A thirty two -item version of the Modern Health Worries (MHW) scale is proposed to assess participants' levels of MHW. (Petrie et al, 2001, 2005, Kaptein et al 2005). Answers are scored on a 5- point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. A higher score indicates increased MHW. A few items of the original Dutch version of the scale were adapted/simplified due to relevance and national characteristics. More specifically, the item "other environmental pollution" was replaced with "climate change/greenhouse effect" and the item "fluoridation of water" was omitted. Cronbach's alpha for this scale was 0.95 (Baliatsas et al, 2015).

7.3.2 C2: Trust in Government and others responsible

This 9 item index is based on Jansen et al, 2018, who compiled a set of questions from Poortinga and Pidgeon (2003), Kraus et al, (2000). On a 5-point scale people can indicate to what degree they agree with each of the statements.

7.3.3 C3: Environmental values

The Environmental Portrait Value Questionnaire (E-PVQ) consists of 17 items containing descriptions, which were based on the so called Environmental Schwartz Value Survey (E-SVS) content, of what another person (gender matched) thought was very important in life. Participants are asked to respond on a 7-point scale (1 not like me at all to 7 very much like me) how much the person in the description was similar to themselves. (Bouman, Steg and Kiers, 2018). While not all items refer to environment or nature, other original items are included here, to allow comparison with other studies.

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7.3.4 C4-5: Beliefs: exposure, perception of chemicals (C4) and of chemicals in the body (C5).

A distinction is usually made between beliefs about the toxic nature of chemicals, beliefs about the personal exposure to chemicals and beliefs about the state of the knowledge about (the risk) of chemical substances. Here only the first two elements are considered as relevant. The beliefs about the toxic nature questions are based on the work of Miles and Frewer (2003,) and adapted by Jansen (2020). The belief about personal exposure is operationalised in two simple questions, adapted from Jansen, 2020.

In the Eurobarometer survey the public opinion on chemicals in the 28 EU Member States was monitored in 2010, 2012, 2016. The aim of the survey was to understand EU citizens' awareness and perceptions of chemical products. The survey includes comparisons (where appropriate) with similar surveys conducted in 2012 and 2010. The results are presented in more detail in the full report. Special Eurobarometer 456, 2017). The questionnaire includes eight questions derived from this survey (items *1129-136*)

In addition, concepts derived from the Myth of Nature (Dake, 1992) were adopted. Thus, four graphs from myth of nature (and cultural theory (Thompson et al, 1990)) were used, with modified labels to represent how the human body might respond to exposure to man-made chemicals in the view of respondents. (items *1147-150*)

7.3.5 C6: Environmental Sensitivity

To assess self-reported environmental sensitivity, a selection of eight items based on the Stansfeld questionnaire (1985) was used, representing perceived sensitivities to environmental stressors such as noise, light, specific materials, colour, smells, temperature changes, cold or warm environment. The answers are formatted in a 5-point scale ranging from strongly disagree (0) to strongly agree (4). The reference period is "during the previous week". A higher score indicates a higher perceived sensitivity.

7.3.6 C7: Health literacy

Health Literacy as defined by the Institute of Medicine (Sørensen et al 2012) is "the degree to which individuals have the capacity to obtain, process, and understand basic health information and services needed to make appropriate health decisions." Worldwide health literacy is considered as one of the most important determinants of health and socio-economic health differences (WHO, 2013). Individual-level environmental health literacy (EHL) was described as: (a) understanding the connection between environmental exposures and health; (b) representations of content knowledge, such as a score on a survey of environmental health knowledge or gains in content knowledge demonstrated with pre/ post-assessments; and, (c) behavior changes reported in response to environmental exposures (Gray, 2018).

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7.3.7 C8: Self-efficacy and (locus of) control

Self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in his or her capacity to execute behaviors necessary to produce specific performance attainments (Bandura, 1989, 1994, 1997). Perceived control (PC) is defined as the belief a person had in their capacity to control (feelings, behaviors, thoughts). Both self-efficacy and perceived control are important mediators in the process by which people cope with challenging or risky situations. While highly related, a distinction is made between perceived control and self-efficacy. The Self-efficacy index is based on a combined index used in the Emphasis project by Baliatsas et al (2011) and in the Frankfurt study (Scheckenberg et al, 2016), comprising a total of five items, adapted for chemicals)

Lack of Perceived Control was measured by using two items from the Life Orientation Test (LOT, Scheier and Carver, 1985) "I am always optimistic about my future" and "I hardly ever expect things to go my way". An extra item was added "If I try I can influence the quality of my living environment", in order to enhance the individual sense of control that can lead to a positive outcome. The score on this 8 item index is rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (0) to strongly agree (4)

7.4 Section D Sources and use of, and needs for information on man-made chemicals in the body.

Section D consists of questions addressed sources of information, trust in these sources, and need for information. Insight into these aspects and the relation of these to risk perception of chemicals in the body may assist researchers in communication of information on HBM levels and associated risks to their target audience/study population.

7.4.1 D1: Sources of Information

Section D1 addresses sources of information where people may obtain or seek information about environmental issues. The list was adapted and translated from Morens et al, 2012. For the different sources of information respondents can indicate the level of trust in the source and whether they would like to obtain information from that source.

7.4.2 D2: Need for Cognition

The Concept "need for cognition" is defined as the tendency for an individual to engage in and enjoy thinking". It is based on the work of Epstein et al (1996) and the Rational-Experiential Inventory of Norris et al (REI-10, 1998). Such information may assist in developing risk communication materials on HBM, e.g. by developing different forms of communication materials targeted to different 'need for cognition' audiences.

7.4.3 D3. Understanding risk information

In this part of the questionnaire people are confronted with a text on HBM. One or more text(s) can be selected by the Principal Investigator, or taken from the HBM4EU factsheets (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/result/factsheets/>), or other HBM4EU texts targeting the general population. Translated HBM4EU factsheets are available in the languages of participating countries.

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Respondents are asked to indicate on a semantic differential (5-point scale) about what their understanding is of the text. Dimensions used are Difficult(easy) to understand, (In)complete, (Un)trustworthy, (Un)common knowledge, (Un)surprising, Disturbing/Reassuring, Complex/Simple, Clarity/Vagueness, Alarmist/Positive, Politically coloured/ Scientific-Objective. This scale is again based on the work of Jansen et al 2020 and Greven, Claassen, Timmermans, Woudenberg, and Duijm (2013).

8 Proposed approaches to statistical analysis

The user/researcher of this template to a self-administered questionnaire on public's risk perception of man-made chemicals in the human body is encouraged to perform a number of below statistical analyses of the collected data. To this end, the user/researcher may adopt their own syntax for the various instruments or refer to the underlying literature to adopt syntax from the literature for external reference.

First step is of course an exploratory descriptive analysis of the distributions of scores on the items in the questionnaire. We suggest breakdowns of the descriptive analysis of section B by sex, age, SES information from section A1. A similar descriptive analysis of sections C and D is suggested. A further exploration of the distribution of section B scores would be breakdowns by health scores of section A2.

A second step would be the mutual comparison of scores on items of sections B1 and B3 so as to assess to what degree perceptions on chemicals in the human body – the main focus of this questionnaire - are rated similarly to or differently from chemicals in the environment. Also, the correlations structure between items in B1, B2 and B3 could be addressed through e.g. Spearman correlations, cluster, principal component or factor analysis (c.f. schematic 1 below). Network analysis may illustrate graphically the association structure among items in these instruments.

Similar analysis can be performed to explore associations among the items in section C (c.f. schematic 2 below).

A more analytical approach is to analyse the associations of section B scores as dependent variables, with a covariate structure of section A, C and D scores. (c.f. schematic 3 & 4 below). Given the number of items in the independent covariates, an exploration of the associations amongst independent covariates is suggested (c.f. schematic 5 below).

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General schematics of items in the questionnaire template, followed by relational schematics for proposed statistical analysis.

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Responses on section D3 will depend in part on the actual example text used to evaluate. Interesting patterns to assess would include the associations of D3 items with A1 and section C items.

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9 Closing remarks

While it is generally accepted that insights in risk perception are a prerequisite for effective risk communication, it appears that, to date, there has been little research into how people perceive the presence of man-made chemical substances in the human body as assessed by HBM, in terms of risks, perceived control and overall acceptability and how do these aspects relate to underlying values, beliefs and knowledge. To our knowledge, no multi-centre studies on cross-cultural differences exist on this topic. Nonetheless, such differences are likely to exist, based on cross-cultural differences in risk perception in general and more specifically in Europe as was shown by e.g. EuroBarometer studies and differences observed in 'environment concern' between European countries.

From the literature, we observe that topics such as personal traits, beliefs about health impacts, trust in authorities, attitudes toward the chemicals themselves and toward dealing with uncertainty, are all relevant topics in the context of risk perceptions, information needs and need for further policy development. Differences in such factors may (partly) explain differences between countries in a multi-country study.

We reiterate that the suggested set of questions in current form need to be tested in panel or pilot study. Before application, these questions need to be translated/back-translated and pre-tested on the target audience/respondents.

References

- Baliatsas, C., van Kamp, I., Kelfkens, G., Schipper, M., Bolte, J., Yzermans, J., & Lebret, E. (2011). Non-specific physical symptoms in relation to actual and perceived proximity to mobile phone base stations and powerlines. *BMC Public Health*, 11(1), 421.
- Baliatsas, Christos, et al. (2015) Actual and perceived exposure to electromagnetic fields and non-specific physical symptoms: An epidemiological study based on self-reported data and electronic medical records. *International journal of hygiene and environmental health*, 2015, 218.3: 331-344.
- Bandura, A. (1989). Regulation of cognitive processes through perceived self-efficacy. *Developmental Psychology*, 25(5), 729–735. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.25.5.729>
- Bandura, A. (1994). Self-efficacy. In V. S. Ramachaudran (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of human behavior* (Vol. 4, pp. 71-81). New York: Academic Press. (Reprinted in H. Friedman [Ed.], *Encyclopedia of mental health*. San Diego: Academic Press, 1998).
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. W H Freeman/Times Books/ Henry Holt & Co.
- Bouman, Thijs, Linda Steg and Henk A. L. Kiers (2018) The Portrait Value Questionnaire (PVQ-21) Measuring Values in Environmental Research: A Test of an Environmental Portrait Value Questionnaire *Front. Psychol.*, 23 April | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00564>
- Briggs, D. J. (2011). "Risk Communication and stakeholder participation in the governance of systemic environmental health risks", vol 13, Nos 3 / 4, 195-215) 13." *Int J. Risk Assessment and Management* 13: 195-215.
- Brown, P., Morello-Frosch, R., & Zavestoski, S. (Eds.). (2011). *Contested illnesses: Citizens, science, and health social movements*. Univ of California Press
- Dake, K. (1992). Myths of nature: Culture and the social construction of risk. *Journal of Social Issues*, 48, 21-37
- Epstein, S., Pacini, R., Denes-Raj, V., Heier, H., 1996. Individual differences in intuitive--experiential and analytical--rational thinking styles. *J. Pers. Soc. Psychol.* 71, 390. Zie uitleg onder
- Eurobarometer_Special_314 (2009). Europeans attitudes toward chemicals in consumer products: Risk perception of potential health hazards. . Special Eurobarometer 314, Dir. General for Communication, EU Commission.
- Fischhoff, B., Slovic, P., Lichtenstein, S., Read, S., & Combs, B. (1978). How safe is safe enough? A psychometric study of attitudes towards technological risks and benefits. *Policy sciences*, 9(2), 127-152. stations and powerlines. *BMC Public Health*: 2011, 11(421)
- Gaab, J. (2009). PASA—Primary Appraisal Secondary Appraisal—Ein Fragebogen zur Erfassung von situations-bezogenen kognitiven Bewertungen. *Verhaltenstherapie*, 19(2), 114-115.
- Gray, K. M. (2018). "From content knowledge to community change: a review of representations of environmental health literacy." *International journal of environmental research and public health* 15(3): 466.
- Greven, F., et al. (2013). Rook bij branden. Aanpassing berichtgeving op grond van perceptieonderzoek. (in Dutch) (Smoke from fires. Adapation of communications based on perception research). Rapport EMGO, VUMC GGD Groningen.
- Istamto, T., et al. (2014). "Multi-country willingness to pay study on road-traffic environmental health effects: are people willing and able to provide a number?" *Environmental Health*: 13:35.

- Jansen, T., Claassen, L., van Kamp, I., & Timmermans, D. R. (2020). 'All chemical substances are harmful.' public appraisal of uncertain risks of food additives and contaminants. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 136, 110959.
- Jansen, T., Claassen, L., van Poll, R., van Kamp, I., & Timmermans, D. R. (2018). Breaking down uncertain risks for risk communication: a conceptual review of the environmental health literature. *Risk, Hazards & Crisis in Public Policy*, 9(1), 4-38.
- Jansen T. (2020) Societal perspectives on uncertain environmental health risks. Implications for risk communication 2020 Academic Thesis, Free University Amsterdam
- Jansen, T. et al. (2020) All chemical substances are harmful; Public appraisal of uncertain risks of food additives and contaminants. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 2020, 136: 110959.
- Jowell, Roger Caroline Roberts, Rory Fitzgerald, Gillian Eva (ed.): *Measuring Attitudes Cross-Nationally. Lessons from the European Social Survey*, Sage Publications, 2007, ISBN 978-1-4129-1981-4
- Kaptein A.A., D.I. Helder, W.C. Kleijn, W. Rief, R. Moss-Morris, K.J. Petrie Modern health worries in medical students *J. Psychosom. Res.*, 58 (2005), pp. 453-457 health and medical care utilization." *Journal of Psychosomatic Research* 51: 395-401.
- Keune, H. L., I.; Bruckers, L.; Bilau, M.; Koppen, G.; Van Larebeke, N.; Schoeters, G.; Nelen, V.; Baeyens, W. (2008). "Monitoring environment, health and perception. An experimental survey on health and environment in Flanders, Belgium." *International Journal of Global Environmental Issues* 8: 90–111.
- Keune, H. M., Morrens B.; Loots, I. (2008). "Risk communication and human biomonitoring: which practical lessons from the Belgian experience are of use for the EU perspective?" *Environmental Health* 7 (SI).
- Kraus, N., et al. (2000). *Intuitive Toxicology: Expert and Lay Judgments of Chemical Risks. The Perception of Risk*. P. Slovic. New York, Taylor & Francis: 285-315.
- Kuhn, K. M. (2000). "Message format and audience values: interactive effects of uncertainty information and environmental attitudes on perceived risk." *J. Environ. Psychol.* 20(1): 41-51.
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. New York: Springer.
- McDaniels, T. L., et al. (1997). "Perception of ecological risk to water environments." *Risk analysis* 17(3): 341-352.
- Miles, S. and L. J. Frewer (2003). "Public perception of scientific uncertainty in relation to food hazards." *J. Risk Res.* 6(3): 267-283.
- Miles, S. F., L.J. (2003). "Public perception of scientific uncertainty in relation to food hazards." *Journal of Risk Research* 6: 267-283.
- Norris, P., Pacini, R., & Epstein, S. (1998). *The Rational-Experiential Inventory, short form*. Unpublished inventory. University of Massachusetts at Amherst
- Petrie, K. J. S., B.; Hysing, M.; Broadbent, E.; Moss-Morris, R.; Eriksen, H.R.; Ursin, H. (2001). "Thoroughly modern worries. The relationship of worries about modernity to reported symptoms, health and medical care utilization *J. Psychosom. Res.*, 51 (2001), pp. 395-40 [13]
- Petrie, K.J., E. Broadbent, N. Kley, R. Moss-Morris, R. Horne, W. Rief (2005) Worries about modernity predict symptom complaints after environmental pesticide spraying *Psychosom. Med.*, 67, pp. 778-782.
- Poortinga, W. and N. F. Pidgeon (2003). "Exploring the dimensionality of trust in risk regulation." *Risk Analysis: An International Journal* 23(5): 961-972.

- Poortvliet, P. M. and A. M. Lokhorst (2016). "The key role of experiential uncertainty when dealing with risks: its relationships with demand for regulation and institutional trust." *Risk analysis* 36(8): 1615-1629.
- Powell, M., et al. (2007). "Exploring lay uncertainty about an environmental health risk." *Public Underst. Sci.* 16(3): 323-343.
- Renn, O. R., B. (2000). *Cross-cultural risk perception research: A survey of empirical studies.*
- Scheckenberg et al, (2016) *Effects of aircraft noise on annoyance and sleep disturbances before and after expansion of Frankfurt Airport – results of the NORAH study, WP 1 'Annoyance and quality of life, Internoise Hamburg, Germany.*
- Special Eurobarometer 456 (2017) – Wave EB86.3 –Chemical Safety TNS opinion & social. European Union, 2016, <http://ec.europa.eu/commfrontoffice/publicopinion>
- Stansfeld S.A., Clark C.R., Jenkins L.M., Tarnopolsky A.. Sensitivity to noise in a community sample: measurement of psychiatry disorder and personality *Psychol. Med.*, 15 (1985), pp. 243-254
- Slovic, P. (1987). Perception of risk. *Science*, 236(4799), 280-285
- Slovic, P., et al. (1995). "Intuitive Toxicology. II. Expert and Lay Judgments of Chemical Risks in Canada." *Risk Anal.* 15(6): 661-675.
- Slovic, P., Fischhoff, B., & Lichtenstein, S. (1980). Facts and fears: Understanding perceived risk. In *Societal risk assessment* (pp. 181-216). Springer, Boston, MA.
- Slovic, P., Fischhoff, B., & Lichtenstein, S. (1981). Rating the risks. In *Risk/benefit analysis in water resources planning and management* (pp. 193-217). Springer, Boston, MA.
- Thompson, M., Ellis, R., & Wildavsky, A. (1990). *Cultural theory.* Boulder, CO: Westview
- TINBER (2019), <https://www.rivm.nl/en/about-rivm/knowledge-and-expertise/strategic-programme-rivm/2019-2022/safety-and-security>
- Ware, John E.Jr. and Cathy Donald Sherbourne (1992) The MOS 36-Item Short-Form Health Survey (SF-36): I. Conceptual Framework and Item Selection *Medical Care* Vol. 30, No. 6 (Jun., 1992), pp. 473-483

ANNEXES

Annex 1: Cover letter to respondents

QUESTIONNAIRE ON RISK PERCEPTION OF MAN-MADE CHEMICALS IN THE HUMAN BODY

Introduction

The European joint project Human Biomonitoring for Europe (HBM4EU) is a collaboration between 30 countries in Europe, the European Environment Agency and the European Commission, and is co-funded under the European scheme Horizon 2020.

Human Biomonitoring is a scientific technique that allows us to assess whether and to what extent people are exposed to man-made chemicals and to what extent these substances have entered their bodies. It involves measurements of man-made chemicals or their reaction to products in biological samples such as blood, urine, hair, mother milk collected from people.

This questionnaire is part of the HBM4EU project (www.hbm4eu.eu) and is primarily aimed at finding out how people evaluate the risk of the presence of man-made chemical substances in the environment and in their body and the personal contextual, and situational determinants of these perceptions. The results will help to improve communication about the Human Biomonitoring studies and will help policy makers in the governance of chemicals.

The study is carried out by [institute Acronym] in collaboration with [Institute Acronym]

The questionnaire has four sections:

Part A on your personal details and your perceived health

Part B on the Perception of risks of man-made chemicals in the body

Part C on general and personal characteristics in relation to risk perception

Part D on information use and needs about chemicals in the body and understanding of this information.

Many questions were adapted from existing questionnaires, to allow comparison with other studies. Therefore, the wording, layout and scales may differ from one question to the other.

It is important that you let us know what you think about these issues and that you hereby choose the answer that best fits your opinion or experience. The first impression is often the best, there are no true or false answers. Your answers will be processed in an anonymous manner.

At the end of this questionnaire you can give your comments on this questionnaire or additional issues you would like to raise.

Thank you very much for your cooperation!

[Name and signature of principal investigator(s)]

Annex 2: Questionnaire items

QUESTIONNAIRE ON RISK PERCEPTION OF MAN-MADE CHEMICALS IN THE HUMAN BODY

QUESTIONNAIRE INFORMATION

ID (PARTICIPANT)	_____
ID (INTERVIEWER)	_____
DATE OF THE INTERVIEW	____/____/____
START TIME	__:__:__
END TIME	__:__:__
PLACE	

A1 Personal information [numbering refers to main HBM4EU questionnaire; note that items 5 and 10

of the main questionnaire are not relevant in this context and not included here]

PERSONAL INFORMATION

1. Name and surname initials:

Gender

1. Male

2. Female

3. Other

2. What is your date of birth

Gender

a. Month

b. Year

3. Were you, your parents and grandparents born in this country, if not please specify where? (include the name of each country

	Here	In another country	Specify country
You	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	
Your Mother	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	
Your father	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	
Maternal grandmother	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	
Maternal grandfather	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	
Paternal grandmother	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	
Paternal grandfather	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>	

4. Which language(s) do you speak at home

Please tick one box

- | | | |
|----|--------------------------------|--------------------------|
| a. | National Language(s) (Country) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| b. | Another Language | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| c. | Specify Language (s) | |
-

6. What is your highest education you completed? [

Please tick one box

- | | | |
|----|--|--------------------------|
| a. | No formal education or below primary education (ISCED 0) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| b. | Primary education (ISCED 1) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| c. | Lower secondary education or second stage of basic education (ISCED 2) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| d. | Upper secondary education (ISCED 3) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| e. | Post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED 4) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| f. | Short-cycle tertiary education (ISCED 5) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| g. | Bachelor's or equivalent level (ISCED 6) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| h. | Master's or equivalent level (ISCED 7) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| i. | Doctoral or equivalent level (ISCED 8) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| j. | Don't know | <input type="checkbox"/> |
-

7 What is your current main labour status?

Please tick one box

-
- | | | |
|-----------|---|--------------------------|
| a. | Employee working full-time | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| b. | Employee working part-time | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| c. | Self-employed working full-time (including family worker) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| d. | Self-employed working part-time (including family worker) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| e. | Unemployed | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| f. | Pupil, student, further training, unpaid work experience | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| g. | Retired | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| h. | Permanently disabled or/and unfit to work | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| i. | In compulsory military community or service | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| j. | Fulfilling domestic tasks and care responsibilities | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| k. | Other namely:
..... | <input type="checkbox"/> |
-

8 What description best fits your current working position

Please tick one box

Definitely
true

a. Manager Employee working full-time

b. Professional

c. Technician or associate professional

d. Clerical support worker

e. Service or sales worker

f. Skilled agricultural, forestry or fishery
worker

g. Craft and related trade worker

h. Plant or machine operator or assembler

i. Elementary occupation

j. Armed forces occupation

k. Other categories
\Specify.....

9 Could you provide the approximate range of your total household income? (It is referred to annual gross incomes from all members of your household) (Indicated by each country)

Income category		Income category	
No.1	<input type="checkbox"/>	No.6	<input type="checkbox"/>
No.2	<input type="checkbox"/>	No.7	<input type="checkbox"/>
No.3	<input type="checkbox"/>	No.8	<input type="checkbox"/>
No.4	<input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>
No.5	<input type="checkbox"/>		

11. In what type of area is your home located (Tick only one answer)

	Definitely true
a. City Centre	<input type="checkbox"/>
b. Near city centre	<input type="checkbox"/>
c. Suburb/metropolitan area	<input type="checkbox"/>
d. Industrial	<input type="checkbox"/>
e. Rural/Village	<input type="checkbox"/>
f. Other areas Specify area	<input type="checkbox"/>
g. Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

A2 Your Health

The following statements concern what you think about your health. How TRUE or FALSE is each of the following statements for you?

		Please indicate for each of the following statements to what degree this applies to your situation				
		Definitely true	Mostly True	Don't Know	Mostly False	Definitely False
12.	I never worry about my health	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13.	I seem to get sick a little easier than other people	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
14.	I expect my health to get worse	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
15.	I am as healthy as anybody I know	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
16.	My health is excellent	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
17.	It is not possible to avoid all risks to my health	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

C Explanatory factors for risk perception (general and personal)

In this section you will find a set of statements about the degree in which you worry about factors in your living environment (C1), and your trust in the government when it concerns regulation of chemical substances (C2).

C1 Worry

Below you find a list of factors in your living environment. Could you indicate for each of them to what degree you are worried about their effects on your health by ticking the box.

Please tick one box per line		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree/nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
68.	Contaminated water supply	<input type="checkbox"/>				
69.	Mad Cow disease (CJD)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
70.	Bacteria in air conditioning systems	<input type="checkbox"/>				
71.	Viruses in air condition systems	<input type="checkbox"/>				
72.	Fluoridation of water	<input type="checkbox"/>				
73.	Vaccination	<input type="checkbox"/>				
74.	Bio-terrorism (e.g. anthrax poisoning)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
75.	Leakage from microwave ovens	<input type="checkbox"/>				
76.	Toxic chemicals in household products	<input type="checkbox"/>				
77.	Amalgam/ Dental fillings	<input type="checkbox"/>				
78.	Medical and dental X rays	<input type="checkbox"/>				
79.	Traffic fumes	<input type="checkbox"/>				
80.	Other environmental pollution	<input type="checkbox"/>				
81.	Air pollution	<input type="checkbox"/>				
82.	Depletion of the ozone layer	<input type="checkbox"/>				
83.	Pesticides	<input type="checkbox"/>				
84.	Noise pollution	<input type="checkbox"/>				
85.	Poor building ventilation	<input type="checkbox"/>				
86.	Nuclear radiation	<input type="checkbox"/>				

		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree/nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
87.	Hormones in food	<input type="checkbox"/>				
88.	Antibiotics in food	<input type="checkbox"/>				
89.	Additives in food	<input type="checkbox"/>				
90.	Pesticides in food	<input type="checkbox"/>				
91.	Genetically modified food	<input type="checkbox"/>				
92.	Radio or mobile phone towers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
93.	Mobile phones	<input type="checkbox"/>				
94.	High voltage power lines	<input type="checkbox"/>				
95.	Overuse of antibiotics	<input type="checkbox"/>				
96.	Drug resistant bacteria	<input type="checkbox"/>				
97.	Lyme Disease	<input type="checkbox"/>				
98.	Contaminated water supply	<input type="checkbox"/>				
99.	To be infected by the Corona Virus	<input type="checkbox"/>				

C2 Trust in regulation of chemical substances

Please indicate to what degree you disagree or agree with each of the following statements by ticking the box

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Disagree/ nor agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
100. The (national) government puts health of the citizens above economic interest	<input type="checkbox"/>				
101. The government is too much influenced by industry regarding regulation of chemicals	<input type="checkbox"/>				
102. The government is sufficiently competent to deal with regulation of chemicals	<input type="checkbox"/>				
103. The government can protect the citizens against the potential harm of chemical substances	<input type="checkbox"/>				
104. The government provides all relevant information about health risks of chemicals to the public	<input type="checkbox"/>				
105. The government is acting in the public interest regarding regulation of chemicals	<input type="checkbox"/>				
106. I feel the way the government is making decisions about regulation of chemicals is fair	<input type="checkbox"/>				
107. National governments and the EU should regulate the exposures, set standards and reduce them to acceptable risk levels;	<input type="checkbox"/>				
108. Industry has the responsibility to replace toxic chemicals by safer ones, regardless of government regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
109. Out of self-interest, industry will limit exposures to safe levels for the population	<input type="checkbox"/>				

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Disagree/ nor agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
110. Regardless of regulations, technological improvements and innovations will automatically reduce body burden to chemicals;	<input type="checkbox"/>				
111. Regardless of regulations, new technologies will lead to new exposures of unknown chemicals, increasing our body burdens of chemicals	<input type="checkbox"/>				

C4 Beliefs, knowledge and feelings about chemical substances

Please indicate to what degree each of the following statements applies to you by ticking the box						
129.	In general, would you say that you are concerned about being exposed to hazardous chemicals in your daily life?	Yes, very much <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes, a little <input type="checkbox"/>	No, not really <input type="checkbox"/>	No, not at all <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>
130.	How informed do you feel about the potential dangers of the chemicals contained in products such as paints, detergents, household products, clothes, furniture, electronics and cosmetics?	Very well informed <input type="checkbox"/>	Rather well informed <input type="checkbox"/>	Not very informed <input type="checkbox"/>	Not informed at all <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>
131.	Do you think that the products containing chemicals that you can buy in your country are safe for human health and for the environment?	Yes, completely <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes, to some extent <input type="checkbox"/>	No, not really <input type="checkbox"/>	No, not at all <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>

132. Compared with 10 to 15 years ago, do you think that the safety of products containing chemicals that you can buy in your country has... Please tick one

1. Improved	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Stayed about the same	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Deteriorated	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

133. Which of the following statements best reflects your opinion...? Please tick one

1. Products imported from countries outside the EU contain safer chemicals than products manufactured in the EU Improved	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Products manufactured in the EU contain safer chemicals than products imported from countries outside the EU Stayed about the same	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. All of them are safe	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. None of them are safe	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

134. Today, in the EU, do you think that the safety of the chemicals contained in products such as paints, detergents, household products, clothes, furniture, electronics and cosmetics is ensured by...? (Multiple answers possible)

• Authorities of the European Union	<input type="checkbox"/>
• National authorities	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Manufacturers themselves	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Other namely	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Other namely	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Nobody	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

135. And in the EU, who do you think should be responsible for ensuring the safety of the chemicals contained in products such as paints, detergents, household products, clothes, furniture, electronics and cosmetics? (Multiple answers possible)

• Authorities of the European Union	<input type="checkbox"/>
• National authorities	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Manufacturers themselves	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Other namely.....	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Other namely.....	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Nobody	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

136. In order to protect human health and the environment from hazardous chemicals, do you think that the current level of regulation and standards in the EU is... Please tick one

• Sufficiently high and could even be lower Improved	<input type="checkbox"/>
• At the right level and should not be lowered or increased	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Not high enough and should be increased	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>

C5 Chemical substances *in your body*; beliefs, knowledge and feelings

Please indicate to what degree you agree or disagree with each of the following statements by ticking the box

		Strongly agree	Agree	Agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
137.	I am aware that a lot of different chemicals are in the tissues of my body	<input type="checkbox"/>				
138.	Given our modern lifestyle it is unavoidable that we are exposed to different chemicals that enter our body	<input type="checkbox"/>				
139.	I think that we should avoid any chemicals from entering our body	<input type="checkbox"/>				
140.	I think most chemicals in my body come from the environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
141.	I think most chemicals in my body come from my food	<input type="checkbox"/>				
142.	I think most chemicals in my body come from my work environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
143.	I think most chemicals in my body come from my lifestyle	<input type="checkbox"/>				
144.	Given my lifestyle, occupation and living environment, the amount of chemicals in my body is well below average	<input type="checkbox"/>				
145.	I sometimes think about the presence of chemical substances in my body, but overall it does not worry me	<input type="checkbox"/>				
146.	I can limit my exposure to these chemicals by personal lifestyle choices (diet, use of consumer products, cosmetics);	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Response of the human body to exposure to man-made chemical substances

The response of the human body to exposure of man-made chemical substances can be symbolized by a ball in a landscape (see figures below). The landscape symbolizes the vulnerability of the body; the ball symbolizes response to exposure. Within each landscape, the ball starts in equilibrium. **Which single picture best describes how you think the human body will respond to man-made chemicals? Please tick the appropriate box (only one box)**

147.	The response of the body to chemicals is unpredictable	<p>1 Unpredictable</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
148.	The body can tolerate chemicals, but only within limits	<p>2 Unstable equilibrium</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
149.	The body is robust and maintains a stable equilibrium when exposed to chemicals	<p>Stable equilibrium 3</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
150.	The body maintains a precarious delicate balance; the least exposure to chemicals may lead to disastrous consequences	<p>Precarious balance 4</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>

C6 Environmental Sensitivity

The following statements are about the way you experience your environment, using the experiences during the previous week as point of reference.

Please indicate to what degree each of the following statements applies to you

		Not at all	Not really	Undecided	Somewhat	Very much
151.	I am sensitive to chemical substances	<input type="checkbox"/>				
152.	I am sensitive to noise	<input type="checkbox"/>				
153.	I am sensitive to smells	<input type="checkbox"/>				
154.	I am sensitive to colours	<input type="checkbox"/>				
155.	I am sensitive to what I eat and drink	<input type="checkbox"/>				
156.	I have a low pain threshold	<input type="checkbox"/>				
157.	I am sensitive for temperature changes	<input type="checkbox"/>				
158.	I do not like it when I feel too hot or too cold	<input type="checkbox"/>				

C7 Health literacy

Chemical substances *in your body* may sometimes cause health complaints or diseases.

Please indicate to what degree you agree with each of the following statements.

Whether a chemical substance can cause disease depends on.....		Fully agree	Agree	Agree nor Disagree	Dis agree	Fully disagree
159.	The characteristics of the substance such as structure or composition	<input type="checkbox"/>				
160.	The features of the substance such as colour or smell	<input type="checkbox"/>				
161.	The amount of the substance in the immediate environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
162.	How often the substance enters your body	<input type="checkbox"/>				
163.	How much of the substance enters your body each time you are exposed	<input type="checkbox"/>				
164.	The duration of exposure	<input type="checkbox"/>				
165.	Your weight	<input type="checkbox"/>				
166.	How healthy you are	<input type="checkbox"/>				
167.	How sensitive you are	<input type="checkbox"/>				
168.	Your genetic make up	<input type="checkbox"/>				
169.	Your gender (male/female)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
170.	Your ethnicity	<input type="checkbox"/>				

C8 Perceived control

With the following questions we would like to ask how much control you think you have over exposure to chemicals and how you experience your environment and how you deal with it

Please indicate to what degree you agree or disagree with each of the following statements

		Strongly agree	Agree	Agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
171.	I am always optimistic about my future	<input type="checkbox"/>				
172.	I do never expect things to happen as I want them	<input type="checkbox"/>				
173.	I have control over the health risks from my living environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
174.	If I make an effort I can influence the quality of my living environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
175.	I can protect myself well against chemicals	<input type="checkbox"/>				
176.	Sometimes I feel I am at the mercy of the chemicals around me	<input type="checkbox"/>				
177.	If I make an effort I can reduce the health risks from my environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
178.	I know how to reduce the health risks from my living environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				

D1 Use of Information

Now we would like to ask you from which source do you obtain or seek information about environmental issues in your immediate environment or life (left column), the degree in which you trust this source of information (2-4th column) and what source would you prefer to obtain information from (5th column)

1. Please tick yes if you use this source of information (no = no tick)
2. Please indicate to what degree you trust this source
3. Which source would you prefer to obtain information from (no information wanted=no tick)

	I use this source	I trust this source			Would like to get information from
	Yes	A little	Moderate	Very much so	Yes
179. Municipality	<input type="checkbox"/>				
180. Regional Government	<input type="checkbox"/>				
181. National Government	<input type="checkbox"/>				
182. Local press(paper, TV, radio)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
183. National Press(paper, TV Radio)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
184. Internet	<input type="checkbox"/>				
185. Scientific literature	<input type="checkbox"/>				
186. A company	<input type="checkbox"/>				
187. My General Physician (GP)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
188. Political Party	<input type="checkbox"/>				
189. My Employer/School	<input type="checkbox"/>				
190. Family, Friends	<input type="checkbox"/>				
191. Environmental Organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>				
192. Action-stakeholder Group	<input type="checkbox"/>				
193. Other, namely.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				

D2 Need for cognition

Please indicate to what degree you disagree or agree with each statement below

		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
194.	I am likely to seek information about the health effects of chemicals and biomonitoring	<input type="checkbox"/>				
195.	I am capable to understand scientific information very well	<input type="checkbox"/>				
196.	I trust my first impression	<input type="checkbox"/>				
197.	If I have to choose I prefer complex above simple	<input type="checkbox"/>				
198.	I trust my intuition	<input type="checkbox"/>				
199.	Thinking is not my idea of having a good time	<input type="checkbox"/>				
200.	My first impression often proves to be right	<input type="checkbox"/>				
201.	Prefer doing things that challenge my thinking skills than activities which require no thinking	<input type="checkbox"/>				
202.	I only trust my gut feelings	<input type="checkbox"/>				
203.	I do not like situations which require thinking	<input type="checkbox"/>				
204.	I can usually sense whether someone is right or wrong	<input type="checkbox"/>				
205.	I do not like to weigh my decisions thoroughly	<input type="checkbox"/>				

D3 Example text

Please insert a text here for the respondent to evaluate. Select from <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/result/factsheets/> were translated versions are available for HBM4EU countries, or insert text from principal investigator.

What do you think about the information you just read on Human Biomarker Monitoring
Please select the answer that best fits your opinion.

I find the information...

206.	1 = Difficult to understand	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 = Easy to understand				
207.	1 = Incomplete	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 = Complete				
208.	1 = Untrustworthy	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 = Trustworthy				
209.	1 = Common knowledge	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 = Informative and new				
210.	1 = Unsurprising	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 = Surprising				
211.	1 = Disturbing	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 = Reassuring				
212.	1 = Complex	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 = Simple				
213.	1 = Vague	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 = Clear				
214.	1 = Too alarmist	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 = Too positive				
215.	1 = Politically coloured	<input type="checkbox"/>	5 = Scientific/Objective				

If you want to add any comments about this questionnaire, please use space below:

Space for comments:

Thank you for participating!